

Non-target effects of bioinsecticides on natural enemies of arthropod pests

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As synthetic insecticides impair the ecosystem services provided by beneficial arthropods, bioinsecticides are gaining interest worldwide as a more sustainable approach to agricultural pest management. Although supposedly considered safe for non-target species, bioinsecticides can still have adverse effects on arthropod natural enemies. This review aims to summarise the literature of the last two years on the non-target effects of botanical and microbial bioinsecticides focussing on the evaluation of lethal and sublethal toxicity to predators and parasitoids. Essential oils show promising compatibility with parasitoids, but their effects on predators are variable. Among microbials, most of the experiments have been conducted with fungi followed by bacteria and viruses with different endpoints, resulting in a general compatibility with biocontrol agents but some results are controversial. Further laboratory studies should be carried out to improve bioinsecticide formulations. Extensive field studies are needed to assess more complex sublethal endpoints at the individual and community levels.

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Introduction

Synthetic insecticides have long been the primary tool for controlling arthropod pests but their indiscriminate and extensive use has harmed non-target beneficial arthropod species. This has led to a rise in the adoption of bioinsecticides which are generally considered a

sustainable crop protection tool and more eco-friendly than synthetic insecticides [1,2]. Biopesticides offer unique advantages in terms of pest resistance management, speed of action, cost-effectiveness, and environmental compatibility. However, many studies have collectively recognised their prospective hazards including the potential harmfulness to the behaviour and physiology of beneficial organisms [2–8].

The majority of bioinsecticides today are derived from entomopathogenic fungi or bacteria, while others are based on plant or microbial secondary metabolites. Although there is an increasing amount of research papers on the efficacy and side-effects of bioinsecticides on target and non-target arthropod species, there is still a lack of alignment on the term biopesticides. A general classification includes living organisms and natural products [5]. The term biopesticides encompasses various pest management tools, such as microbes (e.g. viruses, bacteria and fungi) and their secondary metabolites (e.g. antibiotics), entomophagous nematodes, plant-based extracts (e.g. botanicals), insect pheromones, and even genetically modified crops [5,9]. Nevertheless, the United States Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA) defines bioinsecticides as crop-protection agents derived from natural materials like animals, plants, bacteria and certain minerals. Despite no formal definition of biopesticides occurring at the European level, the Regulation (EC) No. 1107/2009 defines these substances as chemical elements and their compounds that occur naturally or by manufacture, thus including bioinsecticides [10].

For the sake of clarity, only products of botanical and microbial origin having insecticidal properties were taken into consideration in this review, thus excluding pheromones, nematodes and genetically modified plants. Besides, only direct lethal and sublethal effects on natural enemies were analysed, therefore excluding indirect effects such as habitat destruction, damage to nesting, resting, and mating sites [1–3], as well as those mediated by the plants such as reduced or increased attractiveness [11]. While some scientific papers have reviewed this topic over time [3,12,13], a discrepancy amongst studies in toxicity evaluation for bioinsecticides still exists. Therefore, this review aimed to

summarise the latest understanding of the non-target impacts of bioinsecticides on natural enemies of agricultural arthropod pests, and to identify knowledge gaps with emphasis on future perspectives within an Integrated Pest Management context.

Methods used for literature search

A literature search was conducted in October 2024 to identify peer-reviewed and English language papers published between 2022 and 2024 focussing on direct side-effects on pest natural enemies and indirect interactions into additional trophic level. We employed search strings with the following keyword combinations on Web of Science and Scopus databases: ((entomopathog* OR vir* OR “bacter*” OR fung* OR “plant extract*” OR “botanical*” OR “essential oil*” OR “biopesticid*” OR “spinos*” OR “avermect*”) AND (biocontrol OR biological control) AND (*parasitoid* OR *predator*) AND (“side effect” OR “lethal” OR “sublethal”). Studies with laboratory, semi-field, field, and greenhouse experiments were considered, while modelling, simulations and studies involving combination with synthetic active ingredients were excluded. [Supplementary Table S1](#) shows a comprehensive overview of the included studies.

Biopesticide effects on pest natural enemies

Botanicals

Botanical insecticides include a variety of plant-derived products, with essential oils (EOs) being among the most extensively studied on non-target invertebrates [3]. In the last two years, research on the impact of EOs and other plant extracts was almost equally distributed, although EO studies showed a 75 % incidence of negative impacts, significantly higher than the 25 % reported for other plant extracts. These studies were mostly focused on predators (60 %) than parasitoids (40 %) and highlighted that the impact of botanicals can vary depending on the tested formulation, concentration (often estimated on target species rather than natural enemies), and method of exposure, limiting the sublethal assessments to simple endpoints, such as survival and reproduction.

Predators

With regard to other plant extracts (e.g. tarragon, pyrethrin) or their isolated secondary metabolites (e.g. β -citronellol, carlina oxide), different exposures collectively resulted selective towards many predators (e.g. coccinellids, lacewings) in term of acute and sublethal toxicity when tested at lethal and sublethal concentrations estimated on target organisms under laboratory and field conditions [14–18]. However, only neem oil determined high lethal toxicity towards lacewings at different doses [19,20].

EOs exhibit a wide range of toxicities and sublethal effects on beneficial predators, with species-specific responses and varying degrees of impact depending on exposure method, EO type, insect-stage, dose and formulation [21–29]. Residual, topical and ingestion exposure to *Citrus sinensis* and *Cymbopogon nardus* EOs resulted in detrimental sublethal outcomes on lacewings [19–21], while topical and residual exposure of *Allium sativum* and *Mentha pulegium* EOs were harmless towards *Cryptolaemus montrouzieri* adults compared with thyme EO fumigation [22–24]. The negative effects of *Mentha piperita* EO on *Harmonia axyridis* larvae were dependent on both larval stage and dose [25]. Similarly, at low concentrations *A. sativum* EO was harmful to *Nesidiocoris tenuis*, though *Pimpinella anisum* EO had no sublethal effects towards the predator [26]. Interestingly, nanoencapsulated *A. nonum* EO significantly reduced *N. tenuis* progeny without causing direct mortality [27].

Parasitoids

Parasitoids were less susceptible to botanicals than predators, with only 35.7 % and 23.1 % of reports showing negative effects from EOs and other plant extracts, respectively. For instance, neem seed extracts, Lamiaceae EO residues, garlic or mint EOs via fumigation were classified as harmless to Trichogrammatid egg parasitoids, showing low toxicity on emergence rate and adult survival of *Trichogramma chilonis* [30–32], while other EOs, such as rosemary, pepper and lemongrass were selective to Trichogrammatids but were considered slightly harmful on parasitism rate [33]. Similarly, a sublethal decrease in survival and parasitism rates was observed on adult Trichogrammatids treated with EOs based on Annona stem bark or leaf and, although no acute toxicity was reported on adults, stem bark EO was harmful to all parasitoid juvenile stages, while leaves EO exhibited low toxicity only to the egg and larva stages [34].

In the case of Braconid wasps, host exposure to orange, thyme EOs and crude garlic extract at field concentrations did not affect the survival of *Aphidius colemani* developing within treated aphid mummies [35]. However, when hosts were treated with individual or combined applications of plant extracts based on fungatol, gamma-T-ol and neem (at concentrations ranging between LC₃₀ and LC₉₀), the emergence and longevity of adult parasitoids were slightly reduced, although classified harmless according to the International Organisation for Biological Control criteria [36]. Other routes of contamination to botanicals revealed differences in toxicity degree as lemongrass, clove, datura and neem plant extracts applied topically to *Bracon hebetor* adults showed promising compatibility, while parthenium exhibited high toxicity even at low levels [37]. Also, sublethal fumigation with buckthorn EO negatively

affected key life-history traits and other population growth parameters of such braconid wasps [38].

A. sativum EO was found to moderately impair parasitism behaviour and survival of *Necremnus tutae*, while being selective to *Ganaspis kimorum* [39]. Azadirachtin, pyrethrin and *C. sinensis* EO did not cause lethal or sublethal impairment on the efficiency, olfactory orientation and respirometry of *Leptomastix dactylopii* [40]. Interestingly, Hassan et al. found that the effects of botanicals may be strictly dependent on the surfactant mixture as the mortality of *Eretmocerus hayati* developing on whitefly nymphs treated with mustard EO ranged from 80 to 17.5 % depending on the specific formulation tested [41].

Microbials

Regarding case studies dealing with microbials, 63.6 % were focused on metabolites while a low interest was dedicated to entomopathogenic fungi (25 %) and bacteria (11.4 %). Interestingly, 77.3 % of studies on microbials exhibited incompatibility with natural enemies, by which 2/3 were referred to spinosad and avermectins. No studies reported data on viruses. In general, the compatibility of entomopathogens with parasitoids and predators is influenced by many factors, including the time interval between the fungal application and the release of the natural enemies. Infection of insect pests with entomopathogens may affect their physiology and/or their behaviour, thus their intra- and intraspecific relationships including those with natural enemies having an indirect effect in a multitrophic scenario [42]. Scientific pieces of evidence showed that decreasing the doses and applying the natural enemy before microbial inoculation minimise the possible negative effects on various groups of predators [42,43]. Overall, numerous studies indicate that some entomopathogens are generally considered safe for predators and parasitoids while some of their metabolites are not [42].

Predators

According to recent laboratory studies, no negative effects were reported on predators by EPBs. For instance, the soil-dwelling bacterial entomopathogen *Pseudomonas protegens* CHA0 had no impact on larval survival and development, adult emergence or fecundity of *Chrysoperla carnea* through direct and indirect feeding on contaminated prey [44]. Similarly, negligible lethal effects were recorded when *N. tenuis* was exposed to *Bacillus thuringiensis* var. *kurstaki* at field rates [45]. However, *Beauveria bassiana*, *Akanthomyces muscarius* and *Cordyceps fumosorosea* were found to be pathogenic to *Orius insidiosus*, resulting in a significant decrease of its survival while fecundity and searching behaviour remained unaffected [46]. *Beauveria bassiana* conidia at high doses of application induced significant negative effects on *Phytoseiulus persimilis* [42]. Similarly, adults of *Neoseiulus*

californicus exposed to *B. bassiana* showed reduced oviposition period and net reproductive rate at increasing sublethal concentrations [47]. By contrast, the generalist predatory mite *Anystis baccarum* was not susceptible to *B. bassiana* (GHA strain) when exposed to surface residues [48]. Similarly, *B. bassiana* (ATCC 74040 strain) posed no risk to the predator *C. lucasina* and, both *Metarhizium sexmaculatus* and *M. anisopliae* affected neither the foraging behaviour nor the choice of oviposition site in the coccinellid *Menochilus sexmaculatus* [49,50].

The results for spinosad and avermectins on arthropod predators have been controversial. Residual exposure to spinosad at field concentrations was generally considered harmless for *N. tenuis* [45], but topical contamination led to high acute toxicity, reduced fertility and impaired its orientation at sublethal concentrations [51]. Similarly, the flight activity of *Cycloneda sanguinea* was compromised by spinosad through ingestion or residual exposure [52]. Abamectin and milbemectin at LC₉₉ estimated on the tomato russet mite were slightly toxic to both females and juveniles of *Amblyseius swirskii* [53]. Nonetheless, when applied at field rate abamectin was considered selective towards *Neoseiulus barkeri* adults but it showed sublethal toxicity on its eggs [54]. Savi et al. classified abamectin as moderately harmful to *P. longipes* [55], while emamectin benzoate was highly toxic to *O. minutus* [56]. However, both emamectin benzoate and abamectin at field rates were classified harmless to *N. tenuis* [45]. Interestingly, Cherif et al. found a commercial formulation of abamectin having greater toxicity than a laboratory nanoformulation towards the same predatory mirid bug [57].

Parasitoids

A recent systematic review evaluated 49 studies published in 2020–2022 combining a parasitoid with an entomopathogenic microorganism to control target pests [12]. The works included one hundred experiments (84 under laboratory conditions) combining 36 hymenopteran parasitoids with 17 entomopathogenic microorganisms for controlling 31 target pests. *Trichogramma pretiosum* and *Encarsia formosa* were the most frequently studied parasitoids, while *B. bassiana*, *M. anisopliae*, *Lecanicillium muscarium*, *B. thuringiensis* var. *kurstaki*, the *Spodoptera exigua* multiple nucleopolyhedrovirus, and the *Spodoptera frugiperda* multiple nucleopolyhedrovirus were the main microbial agents evaluated. Out of 49 parasitoid–microorganism combinations assessed in the laboratory experiments, 38 were reported as compatible and six as incompatible since a low emergence rate occurred due to bad timing, direct infection, or too high dosage. These studies regarded Lepidoptera, especially Noctuidae, and Hemiptera, Diptera, and Coleoptera. All parasitoids were Hymenoptera, mainly Braconidae and Trichogrammatidae.

Most of the experiments were conducted with fungi (80 %), followed by bacteria (11 %) and viruses (9 %) [12].

Most of the studies of the last two years evaluated the impact of avermectins or spinosad-based bioinsecticides (Figure 1), with 100 % of these studies reporting incompatibility with parasitoids of crop pests. Spinosad at field rate showed high acute toxicity to *N. tuta* impairing its reproductive and non-reproductive behaviour, as well

as juvenile survival [39]. Similarly, *G. kimorum* survival and parasitism rate were significantly impaired by spinosad under both laboratory and field conditions, regardless of exposure route and tested concentrations [39,56,59,60]. Similarly, spinosad residues exhibited high acute toxicity to *L. dactylopii* [40] and *T. japonicus*, showing sublethal impairments on reproduction and circadian activity on the latter [61]. A significant detrimental interaction between spinosad and temperatures was observed on *Telenomus podisi*, with the highest

Figure 1

Sankey diagram showing the interaction flows between the groups of studies focused on different groups of bioinsecticides (EOs, essential oils; EPF, entomopathogenic fungi; EPB, entomopathogenic bacteria), showing compatibility or incompatibility with natural enemies and tested natural enemies according to their ecological functions. The values indicate the number of reports (n = 95) found from the analysed papers (n = 56). Figure was designed in the SankeyMATIC platform.

reduction in emergence occurring at 30 °C [62]. Spinosad was classified as slightly to moderately toxic to *T. remus* [63], while spinosad-activated food baits were harmless or slightly harmful to *Doryctobracon areolatus* adults [64], in both cases in terms of survival, parasitism, and emergence rates. Emamectin benzoate and abamectin were moderately toxic at lethal and sublethal doses on key behavioural and physiological traits of *Tetrastichus howardi* [65] and other Trichogrammatid parasitoids, such as survival, emergence, parasitism and detoxification enzymes [66–69]. However, abamectin was slightly toxic to *Trichopria anastrephae*, although it had no transgenerational effects on their F1 and F2 generations [70]. *Bacillus thuringiensis* var. *kurstaki* reduced the parasitism rate of *T. galloi* females and increased offspring mortality by more than 30 % [58]. However, it had significant effects on the emergence, longevity, and sex ratio of the offspring of the parasitoid [58]. Conversely, a study found that *B. thuringiensis* var. *kurstaki* indirectly affected through indirect host exposure and food poisoning the emergence rate and adult longevity of two *Drosophila* larval endoparasitoids [43]. The biological agent *M. anisopliae* increased offspring mortality by more than 30 % but had no adverse impact on the emergence, longevity, and sex ratio of the offspring. Interestingly, there may be a positive interaction as *B. bassiana* favoured *T. galloi* parasitism rates, therefore it can be used concomitantly with the parasitoid in sugarcane IPM programs [58].

Conclusions and future perspectives

We reviewed a total of 95 study cases in 55 papers. Among these, 51 items (53.68 %) dealt with botanical products, with 20 (39.2 %) exhibiting incompatibility. Overall, there was no correlation between the negative effects of bioinsecticides reported under laboratory conditions and the studied natural enemy functional group (predators or parasitoids). Of 20 cases of adverse effects of botanicals, 60 % involved predators and 40 % parasitoids. By contrast, over 34 cases of detrimental effects caused by microbials, the 47.1 % and 52.9 % were reported on predators and parasitoids, respectively.

The major limitation on the available literature is the prevalence of laboratory-based studies. Out of the 95 studies, only one was conducted entirely in field conditions, while three combined laboratory and field conditions. This significant imbalance would raise concerns about the reliability of the laboratory-based findings as controlled conditions may alter the effects observed in the real agricultural scenario where multiple biotic and abiotic factors can interact. This evidence is in accordance with the meta-analysis by Monsreal-Ceballos et al. based solely on laboratory studies, who also highlighted that the incompatibility of botanicals on parasitoids is regardless the type of exposure route and parasitoid group [71]. Yet, a vast array of plant protection

products and other environmental contaminants that could synergically/additively act to induce more severe harmful effects than single pollutant. Therefore, future research should prioritise field studies and semi-field assessments to improve the ecological relevance of non-target bioinsecticide impact since different biocontrol strategies using both bioinsecticides and natural enemies can coexist and be adopted in the field to reach the final goal of more sustainable agricultural and plant protection practices.

In recent years, more and more evidence has been gathered on the adverse effects of biopesticides on non-target organisms; however, they may still be less harmful than synthetic agrochemicals, and their use should be encouraged after appropriate risk assessment. The assumption that biopesticides are safer than synthetic pesticides can be untrue. Case-by-case risk assessment studies are necessary because pest and beneficial arthropod management is often uncoordinated and may lead to unintended consequences. Conducting more detailed research to assess the effects of biopesticides on a broader range of non-target insects and developing new strategies for coordinated management to minimise negative impacts on beneficial species is thus required. In particular, understanding how biopesticides affect the behaviour and population dynamics of beneficial arthropods is critical for developing long-term pest management techniques that minimise negative consequences as no or few studies have focused on these aspects.

Further research efforts should be devoted to examine the hormetic response at the individual and community levels, including stress response pathways [72–74]. There is a need for more research on the non-target environmental impact of EOs, especially those extracted from plants that are widely cultivated. Nanof ormulation can improve the efficacy and environmental sustainability of EO-based formulations, but more research is also needed on the impact of nanocarriers on non-target organisms [22]. Similarly, as for synthetic pesticides, formulation and distribution methods could help obtain more selective and compatible biopesticides. Finally, further insights could come from the combination of bio-derived molecules with other control methods (e.g. *B. thuringiensis* and RNA-i) to increase both their efficacy and selectivity.

Author contributions

Authors contributed equally to conceptualization, writing, reviewing and editing. FL created the graphical abstract.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coesh.2025.100624>.

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* of special interest

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This review highlights the need for a more holistic approach to understanding the ecological effects of sublethal insecticide exposure. By focusing on community-level impacts and temporal dynamics, this work challenges conventional perspectives on insecticide risk assessment.

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The authors provide a comprehensive overview of the complex interactions between biopesticides, plants, and arthropods, and highlight the potential for optimising their use in sustainable pest management strategies.